

THE ROLE OF INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL ON THE SELECTED TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS COMPANIES OF INDIA

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Abstract

The study aims to assess the intellectual capital of a sample of Indian transport and logistics enterprises while also examining how this intellectual capital affects their financial performance. In order to determine the value addition from this Intellectual capital for these enterprises, this study analysed secondary data from a variety of sources, including the annual reports of these corporations and from websites like money control. Value Added Intellectual Coefficient, or VAIC, is the basis for measuring intellectual capital. Profitability, Turnover, and Market valuation were the three categories used to categorise the firms' financial performance. The profitability of a company is highlighted by its operating ratio, the turnover of its fixed assets is highlighted by its fixed asset turnover ratio, and the market valuation of the company was shown by its market to book value ratio. Data analysis was done using the Panel Data Regression to examine the effect of Intellectual Capital and its components on these organisations' financial performance. To assess if a Fixed Effect or Random Effect test was required for the inquiry, the Hausmen Test was used. The performance of Intellectual capital within the chosen firms was also examined using the One Way ANOVA to see whether there were any differences. The findings of all these studies show that profitability has a positive and considerable impact on a company's intellectual capital, but only a small and positive impact on turnover and market value. The results of the One Way ANOVA test also showed that there was a significant difference in how well the firms' intellectual capital performed.

Keywords: Intellectual Capital, Transport and logistics

INTRODUCTION

The valuable source of competitive advantage for an organisation is considered to be its Knowledge (Use off et al, 2002). The existence of globalized competition recognised the importance of Intellectual capital as a significant power for an organisation to achieve the desired level of economic growth. Intangible assets such as customer information, brand names, reputation, corporate culture, and technology are indications of intellectual capital. This is commonly regarded as a penultimate factor of production, besides the land, labour, and financial capital. In the words of Brennan 2001 and Bozbura, 2005 "Intellectual Capital is stated to epitomize the intangible value driver of businesses and play an important role in the business performance and as an effect on market value". Some researchers consider this to be similar with intangible resources, hidden assets, intellectual properties, knowledge capital, knowledge sources, the invisible value of companies, and so on (Bontis, 2001). Various studies have classified the components of Intellectual Capital, which include Human Capital, Institutional Capital, and Social Capital (Beattie&Thomson,2007, Wall,2005).Martinez-Torres (2006) outlines human capital as "individual level awareness such as professional expertise, experience, and innovativeness which staffs possess."Structural as the organization's

operational system and procedures for decision making and innovation. This has even inculcated infrastructure assets and intangible resources, principles, customs, procedures, and information systems. Finally customer capital as the total of all assets used to organize and manage the firm's interactions with the environment which includes clients, distributors, investor, the competing community, statutory bodies, and community."

Figure 1: Components of Intellectual Capital

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Pew et al. (2007) using the VAIC framework, 150 Singapore stock exchange listed firms were studied about Intellectual Capital and financial performance between 2000 and 2002. The statistical analyses were performed using the partial least square method. The latest findings revealed a link between knowledge Management and a company's current and future performance, as well as its rate of growth. The contribution of IC to company performance varies by industry.

Zeghal and Maaloul (2010) examined the impact of Innovation capital on the monetary and stock market performance of 300 UK companies out from high-tech, traditional, and service sectors. Based on the findings, companies IC have a positive impact on the financial performance of firms in the selected industry. However, the relationship was significant for high-tech industries. Correspondingly, this illustrated that retained earnings remained a major factor in financial and stock prices.

Ahmad and Musharraf (2011) reported a significant association between intellectual capital and enterprise effectiveness in the Iraqi industry. If innovation capital was treated as an independent variable, it included its entire component as dependent variable. The constituents of business performance include advancements, rate of product development, service quality, and overheads. This report's analysis was carried out using a statistical survey of data collection and regression analysis, and finally demonstrated that there was a positive relationship between intellectual capital and business performance.

Narwal & Ramandeep (2014) selected 100 Indian pharmaceutical companies' intellectual capital and significant correlation with business results was studied. The study found that among the components of intellectual capital, structural and physical capital have a positive

influence on company performance, whereas human capital has no significant impact on company financial performance. As a result, the study concluded that Indian pharmaceutical companies continue to rely on physical resources for survival.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Purpose of the Study:

The following objectives were formulated for the current study:

1. To measure the invisible assets efficiency using VAIC method of the selected Transport and Logistics companies of India.
2. To analyse the effects of efficient use of intangible assets and its subcomponents on the business performance of the selected Transport and Logistics companies of India.
3. To assess how intellectual resources affects the business valuation of specific Indian Transport & Logistics enterprises.
4. To investigate difference in performance of knowledge capital efficiency between the selected Transport and Logistics companies of India.

B. Research Hypothesis:

The following research hypothesis has been intended to accomplish the above objectives:

- 1) Intellectual capital efficiency has a no significant impact on the profitability of the selected transportation and logistics enterprises.
- 2) Components of Intellectual Capital have a no significant impact on the earnings and productivity of the selected Transport and Logistics firms.
- 3) Intangible resources do not have a significant effect on the business's valuation of the selected Transport and Logistics companies.
- 4) Components of intellectual resources do not have a major impact on the firm's valuation of the selected Transport and Logistics companies.
- 5) There is a relationship between the performance of knowledge capital efficiency among the selected Transport and Logistics companies in India.

C. Sample Size and Database of the Study:

- 1) The Intellectual Capital efficiency on the firm's performance and enterprise valuation is conducted on selected **Top Ten Transport and Logistics Companies of India listed in Bombay Stock exchange based on their Net Sales for a period of three years ie. From 2019-2021.**
- 2) The database regarding the Transport and Logistics companies of India are collected from the websites of Bombay Stock Exchange and Money Control. Newspaper, Internet sources and Industry Journal are even referred for the purpose of this study.

D. Computation of Variables:

The list consists of all the variables used in this study:

Variables	Abbreviation	Equation
Independent Variables (Intellectual Capital Efficiency)		
Human Capital Efficiency	HCE	Value added/Human Capital
Organizational Capital Efficiency	SCE	Structural capital/Value added
Efficiency of Capital employed	CCE	Value added/Capital employed (total assets minus intangible assets)
Value Added Intellectual Coefficient	VAIC	Human capital+ Structural capital+ Capital employed
Dependent Variable (Financial Performance & Firms Valuation)		
Operating Ratio (Profitability)	OR	Operating Expenses/Net Sales*100
Fixed Asset Turnover Ratio (Turnover)	FTO	Net Sales/Average Fixed Assets
Firms Valuation	MB	Market capitalization/Total book value
Control Variables		
Business's size	B. SIZE	Log of business total assets
Leverage	LEV	Total debt /Total assets

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS:

1. Panel Data Regression: The same unit cross section is measured multiple times in this time series, which combines cross section data. Under this there are two approaches for estimating this which includes:

A. The Fixed Effects Model:

Under this model the intercept of the regression model remains constant over time but varies over cross section and the slope estimates on the other hand remain fixed over the various cross sections and time period.

B. The Random Effects Model:

This model differentiates from fixed effect model from the aspect of underlying values of intercept plus a random variable which varies across cross sections but remains constant overtime.

C. Model for Panel Data Regression:

The following panel data regression has been developed for the purpose of this analysis,

1. The Impact of Intellectual resources efficiency and its sub components on the business performance:

The following panel data regression has been developed for the purpose of this analysis,

$$(a). \text{Operating Ratio (Profitability)} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 \text{VAIC} + \beta_2 \text{ Firm Size}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Leverage}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$(b). \text{Operating Ratio (Profitability)} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 \text{HCE} + \beta_2 \text{SCE} + \beta_3 \text{CEE} + \beta_4 \text{ Firm Size}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Leverage}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}.$$

(c). Fixed Asset Turnover Ratio (Turnover) = $\alpha_{it} + \beta_1 VAIC + \beta_2 \text{ Firm Size}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ Leverage}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$

(d). Fixed Asset Turnover Ratio (Turnover) = $\alpha_{it} + \beta_1 HCE + \beta_2 SCE + \beta_3 CEE + \beta_4 \text{ Firm Size}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{ Leverage}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$.

2. The Effect of Intellectual Capital efficiency & it's constituents on the firms Valuation:

(a). Market to Book value Ratio (Firms Valuation) = $\alpha_{it} + \beta_1 VAIC + \beta_2 \text{ Firm Size}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{ Leverage}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$

(b). Market to Book value Ratio (Firms Valuation) = $\alpha_{it} + \beta_1 HCE + \beta_2 SCE + \beta_3 CEE + \beta_4 \text{ Firm Size}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{ Leverage}_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$.

2. One Way ANOVA:

Thus the hypothesis formulated for analysing the substantial change in the performances of Intellectual capital within the selected sample firms of Transport and Logistics companies includes:

- The performance of the enterprises of the selected Indian transport and logistics companies does not differ considerably from one another.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A. Panel Data Regression:

1. The effect of intellectual capital efficiency and constituents on firm's performance:

Table 3: Correlated Random Effect: Hausmen Test

Test summary	Chi square statistic	Chi Square degree of freedom	Probability
Cross section Random	0.749	3	0.8614

Source: Computed using E views software

Table 4: Profitability (Operating ratio) and VAIC (Intellectual Capital): Cross Section Random Effect

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t statistic	Probability
C	19.003	5.335	3.56	0.0015
VAIC	0.0887	0.075118	1.1813	0.248
Size	0.187	1.314	0.142	0.887
Leverage	-27.39	15.09329	-1.8148	0.0811

Source: Computed from E views software

Significant at 5% level

Adjusted R2 = 0.1509 Durbin Watson statistic = 2.17

Table 3 & 4 represents the panel data regression results for the impact of Profitability (Operating Ratio) on the Intellectual capital of the selected Transport and Logistics Company.

It is found that VAIC is showing an insignificant but a positive association with Profitability (Operating Ratio) as the observed p value of 0.248 is higher than 0.05, thus accepting the null hypothesis inferring that there was no significant impact on the Profitability of the Sample Firms' Intellectual Capital. The VAIC coefficient value can be interpreted as one percent increase in the value of VAIC leads to a corresponding 0.0887 percent change in Profitability (Operating ratio) and vice versa keeping other variables constant. Also Size and leverage is showing the profitability of the has not been affected sample firms. This model is robust as indicated by the Adjusted R square value of 0.1509 or it can be said as 15.09 percent of variance in Operating Ratio can be explained by the model with one repressor i.e. VAIC. The DW static of 2.17 is equal to 2 thereby meaning that the model does not suffer from autocorrelation.

Table 5: Correlated Random Effect: Hausmen Test

Test summary	Chi square Statistic	Chi Sq. df	Probability
Cross section Random	8.49	5	0.131

Source: Computed using E views software

Table 6: Profitability (Operating ratio) and Components of Intellectual Capital: Cross Section Random Effect

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t statistic	Probability
C	-9.185	4.45	-2.05	0.05
HCE	-0.899	0.848	-1.05	0.2997
SCE	0.098	0.660	0.149	0.88
CEE	141.09	12.788	11.033	0.000
Size	0.866	0.5277	1.64	0.113
Leverage	6.64	6.94	0.955	0.3486

Source: Computed from E views software

Significant at 5% level

Adjusted R2: 0.808 Durbin Watson Statistic: 1.0421

The above table shows the effects of each factor on the sample firms' intellectual capital's profitability. The aforementioned data suggests that the Physical Capital Employed is having a favourable and considerable impact on the firm's profitability. The profitability of the sample firms is not significantly correlated with other forms of intellectual capital, such as human and structural capital. Likewise, the influence of the control factors, such as size and leverage, on the sample firms' profitability is positive and negligible. The strength of the model is shown by the Adjusted R square, and it can be seen that C, HCE, SCE, and CEE can account for 80 percent of the variation in profitability. Similarly, the Durbin Watson value of 1.0421, which is less than 2, indicates that the autocorrelation issue is not present.

Table 8: Correlated Random Effect: Hausmen Test

Test summary	Chi square Statistic	Chi Sq. df	Probability
Cross section Random	1.406	3	0.704

Source: Computed from E views software

Table 9: Turnover (Fixed Asset Turnover Ratio) and Intellectual Capital: Random Effect

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t statistic	Probability
C	20.619	27.19	0.75	0.45
VAIC	-0.05	0.400	-0.137	0.8915
Size	0.792	4.398	0.180	0.85
Leverage	-5.367	75.74	-0.07	0.944

Source: Computed from E views software

Significant at 5% level

Adjusted R2 = 0.0046 Durbin Watson statistic = 1.6945

The impact of overall intellectual capital efficiency on the turnover of the selected sample enterprises is shown in this table. Thus, as the p value is less than 0.005, the statistical result shows that the Intellectual Capital measured by VAIC is showing a negligible but positive impact over the turnover of the sample firms. Thus, the alternative hypothesis, according to which there is no discernible effect of intellectual capital on the turnover of the sample enterprises, is rejected and the null hypothesis is accepted. The strength of this model is indicated by the Adjusted R square, and it can be seen from the above table that VAIC explains just 0.46 percent of the variation in Turnover. The issue arises because 1.6945, Durbin Watson's value, is less than 2

Table 10: Correlated Random Effect: Hausmen Test

Test summary	Chi square Statistic	Chi Sq. degree of freedom	Probability
Cross section Random	3.49	5	0.6247

Source: Computed from E views software

Table 11: Turnover (Fixed Asset Turnover Ratio) and Components of Intellectual Capital: Random Effect

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t statistic	Probability
C	33.103	35.02	0.945	0.354
HCE	-4.72	7.15	-0.66	0.515
SCE	1.85	5.82	0.317	0.753
CEE	-36.34	113.48	-0.32	0.75
Size	0.935	4.61	0.202	0.84
Leverage	-8.76	51.68	-0.169	0.866

Source: Computed from E views software

Significant at 5% level

Adjusted r²:0.03 Durbin Watson Statistic: 1.647

The table above shows the impact of each Intellectual capital component. The table above reveals that the p values for HCE, SCE, and CEE are all greater than 0.05, indicating that all three are producing findings that are not only significant but also favourable. Therefore, the

null hypothesis is accepted, meaning that there is no discernible effect of any of the IC components (HCE, SCE, and CEE) on the turnover of the sample companies. The Adjusted R square is equal to 0.03, meaning that all of these factors together can only account for 3% of the variation in turnover. Since the value of Durbin Watson is 1.647, which is less than 2, the autocorrelation issue is not present.

2. The Influence of intellectual capital efficiency and it's components on the firms Valuation:

Table 12: Correlated Random Effect: Hausmen Test

Test summary	Chi square Statistic	Chi Sq. degree of freedom	Probability
Cross section Random	5.11	3	0.163

Source: Computed from E views software

Table 13: Firms Valuation (M/B ratio) and Intellectual Capital: Cross Section Random Effect

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t statistic	Probability
C	8.191	1.54	5.317	0.00
VAIC	0.039	0.022	1.760	0.09
Size	-0.135	0.296	-0.45	0.653
Leverage	-13.848	4.392	-3.152	0.004

Source: Computed from E views software

The contribution of intellectual capital on the firm's valuation of the chosen sample firms is shown here. The p value of the VAIC is thus 0.09, which is above 0.05, demonstrating a positive insignificant impact on the forms valuation, as can be seen from the above table. Therefore, the null hypothesis, according to which there is no discernible effect of Intellectual Capital on the firm's worth, is accepted.

Table 14: Correlated Random Effect: Hausmen Test

Test summary	Chi square Statistics	Chi Sq. degree of freedom	Probability
Cross section random	15.056	5	0.0101

Source: Computed using E views software

Table 15: Firms Valuation (M/B ratio) and Constituents of Intellectual Capital: Cross Section Random Effect

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t statistic	Probability
C	3.28	1.59	2.06	0.05
HCE	-0.048	0.302	-0.16	0.87
SCE	-0.276	0.235	-1.173	0.252
CEE	21.358	4.55	4.684	0.0001
Size	0.044	0.188	0.236	0.815
Leverage	-5.149	2.48	-2.069	0.0495

Source: Computed from E views software

Significant at 5% level

Adjusted r^2 :0.56 Durbin Watson Statistic: 1.55

The above table represents the effect of each constituents of Intellectual Capital (Human, structural and relational capital) on the firm’s valuation. It is inferred from the above table that except Capital Employed Efficiency rest of the two i.e. Human and Structural efficiency is showing an insignificant but a positive impact over the firms valuation of the sample firms. The Adjusted R square of this model represents 0.56 i.e. only 56 percent variation in the firm’s valuation can be explained using all these components. And finally the value of Durbin Watson statistic is showing 1.55 is less than 2 thus the problem of autocorrelation is over come.

B. One Way ANOVA:

The following hypothesis has been framed for analysing the performance of Intellectual capital Efficiency within the selected Transport and Logistics firms:

The performance of the enterprises of the selected Indian transport and logistics companies does not differ considerably from one another.

Table 16: One way ANOVA of selected Transport and Logistics Companies

	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean Square	f value	Probability
Between Groups	128858.864	9	14317.652	540.486	.000
Within Groups	529.807	20	26.490		
Total	129388.671	29			

Source: Computed Using SPSS

The one way ANOVA findings are highlighted in Table 16 to illustrate if there were any appreciable variations in the performance of Intellectual Capital among the identified Transport & Logistics enterprises. Since the p value is below 0.05 and indeed the alternate hypothesis is accepted, it is clear from the above table that there is a substantial difference in the performance of intellectual capital among Transport & Logistics firms. This indicates that despite the fact that all of these businesses are in the same sector, there are differences in the ways in which they approach intellectual resources.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

This Research Paper mainly highlights the Intellectual Capital Efficiency of selected Transport & Logistics on India. For the purpose of this research Ten Transport & Logistics companies are selected based on Net sales for a period covering 2019-2021. Value Added Intellectual Coefficient is used to calculate intellectual capital (VAIC) which is an accepted and verifiable method based on audited financial statements. The objectives for this research are bifurcated into three which includes the following:

A. The Effect of Intellectual Capital and Its Components on Selected Transport & Logistics Companies' Financial Performance:

For the purposes of this study, the three components of intellectual capital—human capital efficiency, structural capital efficiency, and capital employed efficiency—are separated into their respective independent variables. Similarly, the operating ratio for profitability and the fixed asset turnover ratio for turnover are taken into account as financial performance metrics. This study's analysis was conducted using panel data regression with a random effect model that passed the Hausmen test. For this investigation, nearly four models have been developed. Based on such findings, it can be seen that the impact of VAIC, which includes its structural and human components, on a company's financial performance is negligible. However, the Capital Employed Efficiency is having an enormous impact, highlighting the fact that the performance of transport and logistics companies is still reliant on physical assets.

B. the Implications of Intellectual Capital and Its Components on Businesses Evaluation of a few Transport & Logistics companies:

In this case, the market to book value ratio is used to determine how much a firm is worth, and intellectual capital and its components are treated as independent variables. In order to conduct the statistical analysis for this study, four models were created using Panel Data Regression with a Random Effects Model and the Hausmen Test. The findings suggest that the total

amount of intellectual capital, along with its subsets of human and structural capital, has a negligible effect on a firm's valuation. The capital utilised efficiency is one factor that is having a big impact on the value of the company, demonstrating that the companies still place a lot of value on physical assets.

C. An analysis on the variations in intellectual capital performance within the chosen transport and logistics firms:

To determine whether there are any variations in the performances of Intellectual Capital within the firms of Transport & Logistics companies, this study is studied using One Way ANOVA. As the p value is less than 0.05, the results show that there are substantial disparities in the performance of intellectual capital among Transport & Logistics enterprises.

As a result, the study draws the conclusion that the study of intellectual capital has become crucial since the change from the Industrial to the Informational Era. Although it is an intangible by nature, its contribution has grown to be a key factor in the firm's valuation, financial performance, and investment decisions. According to stakeholder theory, businesses with high levels of intellectual capital are better able to create value added than they were in the past.

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